

RAPD and PBR analysis of CMS maintainer and restorer lines in rice

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Recently developed molecular tools such as randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) and polymerase chain reaction-based random fragment

length polymorphism (PBR) are available for characterizing genetic variation and DNA typing of rice genotypes. DNA analysis of three cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines with the respective maintainers (B) and two restorer lines (R) using 12 decamer primers from Operon (OPA-01 to OPA-12) revealed polymorphism only with primers OPA-03, OPA-07, OPA-09, and OPA-12. CMS lines IR67684A, IR58025A, and IR62829A have distinct

RAPD markers in contrast to their B and R lines. DNA polymorphism of A, B, and R lines was also confirmed with PBR in 15 primer/enzyme combinations. PBR reaction amplified a 546-bp (OPA-12) fragment in IR58025A and an 872-bp (OPA-12) fragment in IR62829A lines in a genotype-specific manner. These markers are being developed for identifying genotype-specific DNA markers and mapping desirable genes for hybrid rice research. ■

Transferring wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterility through asymmetric fusion of protoplasts

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We attempted a one-step transfer of wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) through asymmetric fusion between the protoplasts of CMS and fertile maintainer lines. We established embryogenic cell suspensions from the calli obtained from mature seed scutella of a CMS line (V20A), fertile

maintainers (RCPL1-2C and V20B), and restorer IR36 lines. We isolated and cultured protoplasts to produce protocalli that differentiated into plants. Pollen grains of the protoplast-derived plants of the CMS line were sterile, whereas those derived from the maintainer and restorer lines were fertile. To accomplish asymmetric fusion, the protoplasts of the CMS line and fertile maintainer lines were inactivated with 30 krad gamma ray and 10 mM iodoacetamide, respectively. Electrically fused protoplasts divided on a culture medium and formed micro-colonies that developed into calli. These calli also differentiated on transfer to a regeneration medium. We recovered 27 hybrid lines from the fusion product of V20A/RCPL1-2C and 23 lines from

V20A/V20B. Pollen grains from all the hybrid lines were sterile.

Analyses of mitochondrial DNA of the fusion partners and cybrids were conducted by using *orf156* as a probe. This revealed differences in polymorphism between the mitochondrial DNA of the CMS line and fertile maintainers. In the case of *HindIII*-digested DNA, the *orf156* gene was located on a 1.3-kb fragment in the male sterile line, V20A, and on a 12-kb fragment in its fertile maintainers, RCPL1-2C and V20B. A DNA blot analysis of the *HindIII*-digested DNA of all five cybrids showed hybridization of *orf156* to the 1.3-kb fragment. This demonstrated the transfer of mitochondrial DNA from the CMS line to the cybrids. ■

Breeding methods

Adaptability and yield of rice hybrids

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Heterosis in rice was reported in 1926. But commercial exploitation took almost 5 decades mainly because of problems in hybrid seed production. China was the only country to commercially exploit heterosis before 1994. Recently, a few rice hybrids were released in India for commercial cultivation. Although the yield advantage

of rice hybrids is well documented, doubts regarding their yield gains and adaptability over locations still persist. Therefore, we present here the average yield gains obtained from hybrids and their adaptability to locations in India. We used data from 1991 to 1995 on various hybrids tested under different trials over 12 locations in the wet season (WS) and at six locations during the dry season (DS). The yearwise mean yields of hybrids over locations and over trials were calculated separately for both the WS and DS. We identified a hybrid as widely adaptable if it had an overall yield advantage of more than 0.7 t ha⁻¹ over the high-

yielding national check variety Jaya, and we calculated the frequency of such hybrids for each season and year. Percentage heterosis was computed for each year based on the highest yielding hybrid vs Jaya.

The results showed that the overall mean of experimental hybrids increased gradually during the WS from 4.5 t ha⁻¹ in 1991 to 5.5 t ha⁻¹ in 1995; during the DS, yields increased similarly from 5.0 to 6.0 t ha⁻¹. During the same period, the percentage of widely adaptable hybrids in the WS increased from zero to 17%. Similarly, in the DS, it increased from 1.75% (1991-92) to 17% (1994-95). The

maximum yield gain obtained during the WS derived from the performance of hybrids vs Jaya was 544 kg ha⁻¹ in 1991 and 1,522 kg ha⁻¹ in 1995. Similarly, in DS, the yield gain in hybrid rice was 846 kg ha⁻¹ in 1991-92 and 1,634 kg ha⁻¹ in 1993-94. The heterosis for grain yield increased—from 14% (1991) to 31% (1995) in the WS, and from 8% (1991-92) to 27% (1993-94) in the DS. The results indicate that hybrids undoubtedly have a yield advantage over high-yielding varieties such as Jaya. The margin of yield gain increased over the years. The diversity of material added over time may be the reason for such gains. The hybrids are also as widely adaptable as Jaya. ■

Yield stability in rice hybrids

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Hybrid rice technology is considered to have the most potential and be readily exploitable to further raise the yield ceiling in the irrigated ecosystem. But successful exploitation over a large area depends on identifying stable hybrids. Yield heterosis is reported to be a variable trait, which depends not only on parent combinations but also on environmental conditions. Stability for yield of rice hybrids is therefore analyzed. We examined the stability of hybrids for yield in two sets of environments categorized as low and high. Grain yield data of 10 trials conducted between the 1994 wet season (WS) and 1995 WS were used. Locations with a mean yield lower than the grand mean yield were termed low environments, whereas those with a mean yield higher than the grand mean yield were identified as high environments. We analyzed grain yield data on eight hybrids in the 1994-95 WS and dry season tested along with inbred Jaya, Rasi, and IR36 at five locations. The mean yield and coefficient of variation over

seasons and locations were calculated for both hybrids and inbreds to find environment-dependent heterosis.

The mean grain yield advantage of the best-yielding hybrid over Jaya was calculated for each environment. The results indicated that the stability of rice hybrids for grain yield is comparable with that of the best inbred check variety, Jaya. Some of the hybrids, such as IR58025A / IR34686 and IR58025A / IR29723, showed better yield stability over seasons compared with Jaya. But the yield heterosis of the hybrids was better expressed in environments categorized as high. ■

Exploiting heterosis using TGMS lines in intra- and intersubspecific hybridization

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The performance of various thermo-sensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines was assessed in order to use them in two-line intra- and intersubspecific hybridization with wide compatibility lines. Some 26 lines comprising TGMS lines, indica accessions, and japonica with wide compatibility (WC) gene(s) were used to make 65 hybrids: 31 were indica / indica and 34 were indica / japonica (WC). Standard heterosis was recorded up to 58%. Seed yield (g plant⁻¹) ranged from 2.3 to 31.3. The number of heterotic combinations was higher in intersubspecific cross combinations. Spikelet fertility ranged from 2.7 to 88.4% in intersubspecific crosses and from 3.6 to 96.0% in intrasubspecific crosses. The WC lines were not universally compatible in all combinations. The TGMS line ID / 24 was completely

compatible with all WC as well as with other indica accessions.

A molecular phylogenetic map was constructed involving all 26 lines based on the polymorphism generated by 10 random primers—OPD3, OPU7, OPU14, OPZ18, OPZ19, OPZ20, OPA7 + OPA6, and OPA12 + OPD5. By using the un-weighted pair-group method, arithmetic average (UPGMA), a dendrogram was made, taking into consideration the distance calculated based on Jaccard similarity indices. The genetic distances were from 0.2 to 0.88. The height in hybrids increased as the genetic distance between the parents widened. With genetic distance > 0.70 among parents, spikelet fertility and grain yield plant⁻¹ decreased considerably. Heterotic combinations were observed when the genetic distance ranged from 0.4 to 0.7 among parents. ■

Developing CMS and restorer lines of tropical rice hybrids

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The successful development and cultivation of hybrid rice in China in 1976 encouraged IRRI scientists and collaborating countries to intensify this research in 1980. Because the Chinese hybrids and parental lines were not adapted to the tropics, IRRI began collaborating with several tropical rice-growing countries to develop suitable parental lines and hybrids. By 1989, IRRI developed two commercially usable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines that, when combined with easily available restorers among elite tropical indica rice cultivars, produced hundreds of experimental rice hybrids. Some of these yielded about 1 t ha⁻¹ more than inbred checks in national trials under irrigated conditions. By 1994, India, Vietnam, and the Philippines had released some promising rice hybrids for commercial cultivation by farmers. New and better CMS lines are now available in the genetic background of irrigated, rainfed, boro, and